

Who turned on the light? First report of extensive bioluminescent blooms of the heterotrophic dinoflagellate *Noctiluca scintillans* with low abundance of bioluminescent bacteria in the Gulf of Nicoya, Costa Rica

Historically, the Gulf of Nicoya has experienced recurrent algal blooms, including events with the potential to affect marine organisms and human activities [1]. This gulf receives freshwater discharges from the Tempisque and Grande de Tárcoles rivers, together with several smaller tributaries, whose inputs strongly influence circulation patterns, salinity gradients, and the transport of nutrients and organic matter within the system [2]. These processes, combined with the gulf's morphology and water residence time, regulate the mixing of continental and marine waters and modulate the distribution and dispersion of phytoplankton and other planktonic organisms, ultimately influencing their composition, abundance, and temporal dynamics [3–4]. The coastal waters surrounding sites as Paquera, Isla Cedros, Punta Cuchillo, and adjacent areas have exhibited recurrent discoloration events associated with algal blooms for several decades [1,5].

In February 2026, an extensive bloom characterized by intense orange discoloration visible to the naked eye occurred in the region of the Gulf of Nicoya. The bloom formed with continuous surface aggregations with an oily appearance and texture, likely associated with exceptionally high cell densities

observed during the event. These patches were distributed across the water surface and were transported by local currents (Fig. 1). At night-time, strong and intense blue bioluminescence was observed in the Paquera area following mechanical disturbance caused by waves and boat movement (Fig. 2).

During this event, surface water samples were collected both day and night from several locations near Cedros Island (Fig. 1). The samples were analyzed using optical microscopy to identify the bloom-forming microalgae and associated phytoplankton species. In addition, the abundance of total cultivable heterotrophic and bioluminescent bacteria (CFU mL⁻¹) was determined by filtering 5, 1, and 0.1 mL aliquots through 0.22 µm cellulose nitrate membrane filters. These filters were subsequently inoculated onto LSW-70 agar and incubated at 28 °C for 24 h (Fig. 2).

Water temperature during the event ranged from 27 to 28 °C, with a salinity of 32. According to the National Meteorological Institute of Costa Rica (IMN), January and February were characterized by warm and predominantly dry conditions typical of the North Pacific dry season. Persistent northeasterly winds were recorded, with moderate to strong intensity (30–40 km h⁻¹), to-

gether with mostly clear skies. Several cold front events occurred in February, which further enhanced wind activity in the region.

Sample analyses revealed that the bloom was produced almost exclusively by the heterotrophic dinoflagellate *Noctiluca scintillans*, whose size ranged from 180 to 250 µm (Fig. 2). Minor amounts of the dinoflagellate *Prorocentrum micans* and the central diatom *Stephanocyclus meneghinianus* (= *Cyclotella meneghiniana*) were observed. As the water samples were highly concentrated with *N. scintillans*, accurate cell counting was difficult; therefore, several counts were performed using Utermöhl chambers, yielding concentrations of 1.7×10^3 to 1×10^6 cells L⁻¹.

Noctiluca scintillans is a heterotrophic dinoflagellate that feeds on diatoms and bacteria, among other organisms. However, both in the water samples and inside *Noctiluca* cells, a high abundance of the planktonic ciliate *Strombidium* sp. was observed. This oligotrich ciliate is approximately 20 µm in diameter, and functions as a microzooplankton grazer feeding on bacteria and pico- to nanophytoplankton, and is commonly abundant in coastal and oceanic waters (Fig. 2). Although not previously reported in the Gulf of Nicoya, it is a widespread component of marine microzooplankton and plays a key role in microbial food webs. *Strombidium* spp. consume small dinoflagellates and diatoms and can exert grazing pressure on phytoplankton blooms. However, this effect is limited when blooms are dominated by larger dinoflagellates such as *N. scintillans*, which is itself a predator of smaller plankton. Consequently, in systems such as the Gulf of Nicoya, *Strombidium* may contribute to the regulation of small phytoplankton, but its effect diminishes under blooms dominated by *N. scintillans*.

Strombidium is associated with relatively oligotrophic environments, thriving in nutrient-poor tropical or subtropical waters. It is widely distributed in tropical, subtropical, and temperate

Fig. 1. Extensive orange-colored patches produced by the dinoflagellate *Noctiluca scintillans* around Cedros Island and the Gulf of Nicoya. (A) Map of the Gulf of Nicoya (9°49'09" N and 84°55'56" W). (B, C) Extensive patches with orange coloration (photographs by Marisol Hidalgo Prado).

Fig. 2. Dominant dinoflagellate of the *Noctiluca scintillans* algal bloom around Cedros Island. (A) Bloom of *N. scintillans*. (B) Ciliate fed on by *Noctiluca*, *Strombidium* sp. (C) Culture of bioluminescent bacteria. (D, E) bioluminescence observed at night on Cedros Island and surrounding areas (photographs by Pablo Novoa Villegas).

seas and contributes significantly to microbial recycling and the regeneration of dissolved and particulate organic matter, thereby sustaining ecosystem productivity [6]. For this reason, it is often used as an indicator of microbial recycling, as well as the balance between primary and bacterial production.

Although the Gulf of Nicoya may present relatively oligotrophic conditions in certain areas and certain seasons, mainly during the dry season (December–March), it is not a typical oligotrophic system. The estuary is characterized by strong tidal influence and significant riverine inputs, especially during the rainy season (May–November), resulting in a highly dynamic estuarine mixing system [3]. Its high primary productivity in the inner basin is strongly influenced by tidal cycles and riverine input. These conditions favour the development of dinoflagellate blooms associated with strong trophic variability.

In this context, the extensive *N. scintillans* bloom did not depend solely on dissolved nutrient concentrations, as this species typically feeds on smaller plankton and benefits from stable surface waters where it accumulates. In addition, high concentrations of *Strombidium* sp. may have contributed indirectly to the formation of blooms throughout the area. Bacterial counts ranged from 48 to 840 CFU mL⁻¹, while bioluminescent bacteria did not exceed 2 CFU mL⁻¹. This low abundance suggests relatively oligotrophic conditions

in areas adjacent to Cedros Island. This condition may contribute to the persistence of bioluminescent events, with episodic intensification driven by nutrient pulses associated with oceanographic dynamics such as wind-induced mixing. It has been shown that nutrient availability controls the abundance and structure of marine bacterial communities, with lower densities observed in oligotrophic environments [7]. Although further research is required to understand microbial interactions in this system, the low abundance of bioluminescent bacteria suggests that the observed luminescence is primarily associated with the trophic dynamics of *N. scintillans*. While historical records include bioluminescent events driven by high densities of luminous bacteria over large oceanic regions (“Milky Seas”), these produce a continuous, homogeneous glow consistent with bacterial emission [8]. In contrast, dinoflagellate bioluminescence is characterized by short flashes or bursts triggered by mechanical stimulation [9], as observed here.

Although *N. scintillans* blooms have previously been reported with reddish coloration in the Gulf of Nicoya, this is the first observation of a dense bloom with intense orange coloration. These blooms consistently exhibit strong nocturnal bioluminescence. An additional previously undocumented feature in this region is the oily or viscous tactile sensation during intense bloom conditions, associated with dense surface ag-

gregations and mucilaginous material. At high densities, *N. scintillans* can produce significant amounts of ammonia and organic compounds, contributing to altered water texture [10].

The bioluminescent blooms of *N. scintillans* in the Gulf of Nicoya represent ecologically significant phenomena of increasing scientific and touristic interest. These events have contributed to the development of local ecotourism activities based on bioluminescence observation. Although *N. scintillans* is not considered directly toxic to humans, it may cause indirect ecological impacts through oxygen depletion and fish mortality associated with organic matter degradation and bacterial activity.

The occurrence of *N. scintillans* blooms in this region appears to be influenced by seasonal temperature increases and nutrient inputs associated with wind-driven mixing. Bioluminescence is observable only under mechanical disturbance but can be visible under moonlight or boat illumination. Its extreme luminosity has been proposed to play an adaptive role in predation or intraspecific communication.

The recent bloom highlights the sensitivity and ecological complexity of estuarine systems. Such events demonstrate how relatively small variations in climate, circulation, and nutrient inputs can trigger large-scale responses across planktonic and microbial food webs.

Understanding these dynamics is essential for assessing productivity, biodiversity, and environmental change in

estuaries supporting fisheries, tourism, and biodiversity. Monitoring these processes allows differentiation between benign and harmful blooms and supports the preservation of ecosystem integrity. Ultimately, such phenomena not only expand scientific understanding but also underscore the resilience and fragility of tropical coastal ecosystems.

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